

Report

Technical photography and photogrammetry applied to the Tomb of Philip II at Vergina, Greece

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Abstract

This report describes the documentation work carried out on the frieze of the Macedonian tomb of Philip II at Vergina (Greece), conducted within the framework of transnational access activities to the MOLAB platform of the European project IPERION-HS. The work was performed using an integrated approach combining technical photography and photogrammetry for the HFTV-ReVis project: “XRF mapping measurements, XRD, CXRF and photogrammetry on the tomb of Philip II”, carried out from 7 to 14 March 2023.

Photographic documentation and photogrammetric processing enabled the generation of an unprecedented three-dimensional access model of the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II, characterized by very high metric accuracy and previously unattained plastic and graphic detail.

This methodological approach improved the quality of the final imaging, revealing details imperceptible to the naked eye, such as the clearly defined contours of the different plaster applications and existing fractures, allowing precise mapping for the analysis of the frieze’s crack pattern.

These analyses provide valuable data that enrich scientific studies and support targeted conservation and restoration interventions, making a significant contribution to the preservation and enhancement of cultural heritage.

Introduction

In the field of archaeology and cultural heritage, photography represents a non-invasive and easily accessible technology for the digitalization of objects and pictorial works with complex geometries. Thanks to its ability to provide an exceptional level of detail, the digital model produced through technical photography constitutes an essential basis for the study, documentation, enhancement, and conservation of objects and works of scientific and cultural heritage interest.

Achieving a high level of detail is possible through the combination of technical photography and the application of photogrammetric methodologies. It is essential to master not only acquisition tools—such as cameras, lenses, and lighting systems—but also photogrammetric processing software and techniques, which make it possible to optimize results and effectively manage the acquired data. Through these skills, it is possible to create three-dimensional models with very high precision in geometry, color, and texture.

A significant example of this synergy between photogrammetry and technical photography is the digitization work carried out on the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II at Vergina, Greece. In this digitization project, the combination of technical knowledge and methodological awareness made it possible to obtain a three-dimensional digital model of extraordinary precision.

The materialization of the digital model required careful planning and experimentation, as well as the adoption of advanced photographic and photogrammetric techniques, articulated in the

following phases: setup experimentation, photographic acquisition, photogrammetric processing, and 2D and 3D visualization.

Methodology

In the laboratory, experimental tests were conducted to obtain imaging with an optical resolution below 100 microns, determining a distance of approximately 50 cm between the camera and the surface of the frieze (Fig. 1). This distance proved essential for balancing flash power and selecting the most effective aperture to achieve sufficient depth of field to keep the entire image in focus in each single shot, without resorting to focus stacking techniques.

Various movement configurations for the camera-lighting setup were tested in order to preserve planarity between images during acquisition. To ensure uniform illumination and control reflections on the painted surface, cross-polarized lighting was adopted.

Finally, to minimize dependence on electrical power and the use of cables, the entire system was designed to operate with integrated batteries (camera, flash units, triggers, receivers), also optimizing overall bulk during photographic acquisition.

Fig. 1 – (a) Experimental laboratory setup at a distance of 60 cm; (b) Digitized area; (c) Detail; (d) Optimal resolution detail.

Photographic Acquisition System and Movements

The acquisition system consists of two main modules. The first module comprises a Canon EOS 200D camera mounted vertically on a horizontal bracket, flanked by two flash units positioned on the right and left, inclined at 45° relative to the shooting point. The camera angle is always perpendicular to the plane, and each single shot covers an area of approximately 13×18 cm. This configuration ensures balanced illumination and reduces shadows, also thanks to the use of cross-polarized lighting: both the light sources and the camera are equipped with polarizing filters, ensuring a reflection-free rendering of the surface—an essential condition for faithful reproduction of surface details.

The second module consists of a vertically sliding column integrated with a horizontal slider. The first module is mounted on the second, which in turn is fixed to a tripod to ensure stability and mobility. Through the combination of vertical and horizontal movements between the two modules, the system achieves a shooting coverage of 120 cm in height and 60 cm in width, while maintaining a constant distance between the camera and the frieze during acquisition.

To cover the entire frieze, acquisitions were organized progressively in groups (from 50×50 cm to 120×60 cm), as illustrated in Fig. 2. The sequence starts from group 029 and ends with group 043, the latter acquired to close the entire perimeter (although not used in the 3D reconstruction). To ensure merging between different sets and reduce possible gaps, a significant overlap between acquisition groups was maintained.

Fig. 2 – Mapping of acquisition groups.

Materials Used

- * Canon 200D – 24 MP
- * Canon MTF 40 mm MACRO f/2.8 lens
- * 40 cm bracket
- * Camera polarizing filter
- * Light source polarizing filters
- * 2 × Godox V1 flash units
- * 60 cm vertical column
- * Manfrotto arm
- * 60 cm horizontal slider
- * Manfrotto #400 head
- * Manfrotto #055 tripod
- * Agisoft Metashape

Editing and Post-Processing

For editing and post-production, Capture One Pro software was used. Images were calibrated for color temperature and brightness equalization. During editing, 7,500 images were selected from the 10,000 shots acquired, ensuring an unprecedented level of detail for the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II. These were then converted to JPG format at maximum quality (100%). This choice minimizes undesirable effects associated with JPG compression, which could cause detail loss and visual artifacts. Using maximum quality significantly reduced the risk of pixel displacement or image degradation, preserving image integrity for subsequent processing phases. Images that were redundant or affected by technical defects, such as focus errors or inadequate lighting, were discarded.

Once the final dataset was selected, optimized images were imported into Agisoft Metashape (Fig. 3) to generate an ultra-high-resolution point cloud. The processing workflow was divided into separate groups to manage the large data volume, which were later merged into a single digital model. This approach ensured an extremely accurate and detailed representation of the frieze, preserving its original characteristics.

Fig. 3 – Digital model processing in Agisoft Metashape.

Export and Applications

The digitization of the frieze, understood as the transformation of the real object into a virtual model in the form of a point cloud, produced a very high-resolution 3D model. To enable sharing across different systems, as well as interactive visualization and detailed analysis in Potree [Schütz, M. (2016)] (Figs. 4, 5, 6), the model was exported in LAS format.

The LAS format is an open standard developed by ASPRS for managing 3D point clouds. Although not open source, its specifications are publicly available and supported by open-source implementations such as PDAL. It integrates essential information such as spatial coordinates, intensity values, and classifications, ensuring interoperability with a wide range of GIS and photogrammetric software. Its binary structure and compression capability (LAZ) optimize file size and reduce processing time. This approach facilitates data exchange, long-term preservation, and interdisciplinary analysis [ASPRS (2019)].

Fig. 4 – Potree Point Cloud Viewer visualization, detail of the frieze surface from the point cloud.

Fig. 5 – Potree Point Cloud Viewer visualization, detail of painted surface and plaster degradation with profile.

Fig. 6 – Potree Point Cloud Viewer visualization, detail of the Greek key and stepped classical cornice with profile.

In addition to the three-dimensional model, Agisoft Metashape enabled the generation of a visible-light (VIS) orthophoto and a Digital Surface Model (DSM) in TIFF format. These 2D products of the frieze, intended for academic purposes, can be consulted using image-editing software such as Gimp, Affinity Photo, or Photoshop, or with common image viewers such as Preview or Photos. They can also be visualized or shared on online image-delivery platforms such as IIF or KR pano.

An example of access created for the visualization of white-light images and the Digital Surface Model is available at: http://www.fotografiatecnica.it/verghina_sfm/index.html

The exported formats offer a wide range of applications, including scientific research, dissemination, and digital documentation, while ensuring long-term data preservation and the possibility of future processing, interaction, and interpretation.

Results

The 2D and 3D photographic documentation of the frieze produced results of exceptional significance, offering unprecedented chromatic and plastic imaging and enabling the creation of a three-dimensional model without precedent for the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II. Thanks to the intensive high-resolution photographic campaign conducted over the entire surface of the frieze (5.50 × 1.20 m), extremely accurate metric restitution was achieved, with a definition capable of rendering visible details down to 100 microns.

Processing 7,500 photographic acquisitions with Agisoft Metashape generated an overall point cloud of 1,209,709,838 points, making it possible to create a three-dimensional access model capable of describing the overall morphology of the entire frieze with extreme precision.

From the three-dimensional access model of the frieze, two computational imaging products were derived: an orthophoto and a Digital Surface Model (DSM), both with a resolution of 60,000 × 15,000 pixels—equivalent to a photographic image produced by a 900-megapixel camera. Comparison between visible-light imaging and DSM imaging highlighted distinctive aspects of the structure and morphological characteristics of the frieze surface, making it possible to identify the

contours of the probable progressive application of plaster, as well as the complete crack pattern and traces of plastic-pictorial and restoration interventions (Figs. 7a, 7b, 8a-b, 9a-b). These results provide new essential interpretative clues for better understanding the execution process of the artwork, enabling a transition from purely visual assessment to quantitative and detailed surface analysis.

The integrated application of Technical Photography and Photogrammetry provides a comprehensive and in-depth view of the frieze, offering a highly precise and versatile digital representation. This approach allows the analysis of otherwise inaccessible details, making documentation an indispensable tool for advanced scientific studies, planned conservation interventions, and effective dissemination of cultural heritage.

Fig. 7a – Digital Surface Model processing with dashed contours indicating possible progressive plaster application.

Fig. 7b – Digital Surface Model processing.

Fig. 8a-b – Detail of plastic-pictorial interventions and areas of painted surface degradation.

Fig. 9a-b – Detail of conservation intervention – probable use of Paraloid.

Conclusions

The methodological solutions adopted made it possible to produce an extremely detailed and accurate digital model of the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II at Vergina, faithfully reproducing both graphic characteristics and structural elements. The use of technical photography in support of photogrammetry proved to be a highly effective and versatile approach for cultural heritage surveying.

The dialogue between photogrammetry and photographic techniques is fundamental, as each situation requires a specific methodology, often developed ad hoc for the application context. This approach should not be understood as a standardized system, but rather as a creative and flexible method. In the case of Vergina, the harmonization between technique and method demonstrated its validity, highlighting how an innovative approach can yield excellent results even in complex scenarios such as the frieze of the Tomb of Philip II.

Thanks to this digital model, it will be possible to carry out in-depth analyses, experiment with virtual restoration interventions, and develop dissemination materials, making a significant contribution to the conservation and enhancement of cultural heritage. The result represents a reliable reference point for conservators, archaeologists, art historians, and specialists from other disciplines, fostering knowledge sharing and ensuring more informed and comprehensive protection of the cultural asset.

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